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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE CLUSTER SYSTEM IN THE AGRICULTURAL FIELD

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Abstract: The cluster principle of formation of new economic structures is justified in the article. The conditions, reasons and mechanisms for the creation of network structures are analyzed. On the basis of the cluster scheme, the characteristics and advantages of production, as well as the factors hindering the development of their activity, were analyzed.

Key words: cluster, innovation, cluster approach, innovative activity.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yangi iqtisodiy tuzilmalarni shakllantirishda klaster tamoyili asoslab berilgan. Tarmoq tuzilmalarini yaratish shart-sharoitlari, sabablari va mexanizmlari tahlil qilingan. Klaster sxemasi asosida ishlab chiqarish faoliyatining xususiyatlari va afzalliklari, shuningdek, ularning rivojlanishiga to'sqinlik qilayotgan omillar tahlil etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: klaster, innovatsiya, klaster yondashuvi, innovatsion faoliyat.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В статье обоснован кластерный принцип формирования новых экономических структур. Проанализированы условия, причины и механизмы создания сетевых структур. На основе кластерной схемы рассмотрены особенности и преимущества производства, а также факторы, препятствующие развитию их деятельности.

Ключевые слова: кластер, инновации, кластерный подход, инновационная деятельность.

INTRODUCTION

In our country, consistent measures are being taken to reform the agrarian sector, and to introduce market mechanisms and modern technologies into it. In particular, the cluster method was introduced, and the types of crops were changed based on the needs of the time. As a result, both productivity and income are increasing.

More than 80 types of agricultural products grown in our country are exported to 66 countries. By the Decree of the Head of State dated 2019–10–23, the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2030 was adopted. In accordance with it, fruit and vegetable clusters are being organized in order to produce products with high added value.

On 2019–12–11, the President's decision in this regard was adopted, and all organizational and legal foundations were created. What is the advantage of the cluster system for the establishment of 86 such clusters by local governments in a short time? It allows not only the sale and export of raw materials, but also finished products, which are beneficial to both the state and the producer.

Another advantage of the cluster system is that enterprises can freely use the products produced and independently determine prices and sales volumes, taking into account the interests of all employees.

At all stages of socio-economic development and in all countries, the basis of human life is the production of material goods and the provision of services. Without the processes of production and service, there would be no goods to exchange, distribute, or consume. Humanity, in any society, cannot live without consumption, nor can it live without production. This issue has become a major problem for countries around the world today.

Every company tries to reduce its costs. At the current stage of our country's development, increasing the export potential and the competitiveness of our national economy largely depends on achieving savings and reducing the cost of products and services. Accordingly, in 2020, it was rightly emphasized: "We continue our studies and research on increasing the interests of farmers and peasants in agriculture. Advanced technologies and a cluster system are being introduced into the industry."

The use of advanced techniques and technologies in the production process is important not only for the development of the cluster system in Uzbekistan's economy but also for the effective functioning of entrepreneurs and the agricultural sector. In the current conditions, production efficiency is the main factor in the development of Uzbekistan's economy. Effective use of this factor is one of the key ways to ensure the stable development of the cluster system in our country.

In the context of accelerating reforms and increasing globalization of the world economy, our country must make a rapid transition to an innovative model for developing the cluster system in the short term and bring this strategically important branch of the economy to a level that meets the requirements of the time. Otherwise, the cluster system will lag behind in development and will not be competitive.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Many scientists in foreign countries and in our country deal with the issue of managing the competitiveness of countries' economies. Although it has not been long since the cluster approach to the organization of production began to be used in our country, the founders of the theory of competition abroad have been developing this direction for a long time. The scientific basis for ensuring the competitiveness of countries in international trade was developed by Adam Smith, the founder of the classical school, in his theory of absolute advantage, and later his student D. Ricardo developed the theory of comparative advantage.

Michael Porter is the founder of the theory of using cluster schemes in competitive management. According to Michael Porter, the competitiveness of the economy of a country or region depends not on such factors as the exchange rate, interest rate, budget deficit, cheap labor, or natural resources, but on production productivity. As productivity growth in production enterprises requires the regular development of the economy, it is necessary for enterprises in various sectors to improve the production process by increasing the quality of products, expanding consumer properties, developing technologies, and enhancing production efficiency.

Porter developed the determinants of a country's competitive advantages by grouping them into four categories: factor conditions, demand conditions, related and supporting industries, and firm strategy, structure, and rivalry. There is a correlation and a direct proportional relationship among these factors. As a unique instrument for ensuring competitiveness, cluster schemes are proposed, which are defined as a group of closely related companies and associated organizations that operate together and complement each other within the same field.

Later, this theory was further developed in the studies of F. Raines. F. Raines's economic views on competitiveness, like those of M. Porter, are mainly based on improving the quality indicators of the production process and products. In this regard, the practice of creating cluster schemes was developed based on the experience of countries with long-established market economies.

Various aspects of increasing the competitiveness of the national economy and its sectors in Uzbekistan, as well as the theoretical and methodological bases of cluster formation and related organizational issues, have been studied in the scientific research of G. Zakhidov. In these studies, the cluster scheme of production organization was analyzed as an important instrument for implementing the country's regional policy and enhancing the competitiveness of various sectors of the economy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research employs a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative analyses to assess the effectiveness of the cluster system in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan, with a specific focus on cotton–textile clusters in the Tashkent region. The study draws upon official statistical data provided by the Ministry of Agriculture and other open-source government reports, presidential decrees, and policy documents, particularly the Strategy for Agricultural Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2030.

A descriptive–analytical method is used to examine the development and practical implementation of cluster initiatives, while comparative economic analysis is applied to evaluate productivity indicators, profitability, and export potential of agricultural clusters, especially in cotton production. The performance of individual clusters, such as “TCT Agrocluster” in Kuyichirchik district, is analyzed in terms of land utilization, yield per hectare, fulfillment of contractual obligations, and integration of advanced technologies.

The research also involves a literature review of both domestic and foreign academic sources. Foundational theories of competitiveness, such as those proposed by Adam Smith, David Ricardo, and Michael Porter, are explored to construct the theoretical basis of cluster competitiveness. Porter's Diamond Model is referenced as a key framework to assess the competitive advantage of regional economies through cluster mechanisms.

Moreover, a comparative analysis of Uzbekistan's agricultural performance with that of developed countries (e.g., the Netherlands) is conducted to highlight the gap in productivity and to justify the need for innovation-led cluster development. Empirical data from 2020 on land use and cotton production by 96 cotton–textile clusters is analyzed to validate the economic rationale behind expanding the cluster model.

Through this methodology, the study aims to identify the economic advantages of the cluster system, its role in enhancing production efficiency, value addition, employment, and interregional integration, and to propose policy implications for the further sustainable development of agricultural clusters in Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Cotton-Textile Clusters Located in Tashkent Region

No	Cotton-textile production and clusters	Name of districts	Area of cotton, hectares
1	“Oqqorgon Agro Cluster” MChJ	Oqqorgon	5,407,0
2	“APK Bekobod” MChJ	Bekobod	12,000,0
3	“APK Boka” MChJ	Boka	12,131,0
4	“TCT Agro Cluster” MChJ	Kuyichirchik	10,000,0
5	“Textile Technologies Group” XK	Chinaz	6,200,0
6	“Kokcha Tekstil” MChJ	Ortachirchik	9,270,0
	Total		55,008,0

In 2020, 906,313 hectares of land were cultivated with raw cotton by cotton-textile production enterprises and clusters. This represents 87.7% of the total land area used for cotton cultivation in the Republic. These enterprises and clusters increased cotton productivity by 10 centners per hectare through the implementation of advanced, modern, and innovative technologies during the cultivation of raw cotton.

Why cotton farming? It is natural for this question to arise. Cotton products constitute nearly half of the gross output produced in the agricultural sector. However, analyses show that there are significant untapped opportunities and unresolved issues within the cotton farming industry. It can be said that cotton production remains the least profitable among all branches of agriculture. The cotton yield rate in our Republic is considerably lower compared to that of other cotton-producing countries. Nonetheless, analysis indicates there is tremendous potential to increase productivity per hectare in irrigated cotton-growing areas.

The need to identify effective methods for producing raw cotton is further underscored by the fact that Uzbekistan’s land productivity potential remains underutilized. This becomes especially evident when agricultural indicators of Uzbekistan are compared with those of developed countries. For example, the Netherlands — with a population of 16 million and 1.038 million hectares of cultivated land (60 percent of which is reclaimed coastal land) — produces agricultural products worth 131 billion USD. Meanwhile, Uzbekistan, with a population of 32 million and 4.4 million hectares of cultivated land, produces only 13.2 billion USD worth of agricultural output.

The primary consumer of raw cotton in Uzbekistan is the textile industry, which plays a crucial role in the industrial complex of the Republic. Based on this, the development of the textile sector is directly linked to the state and performance of the cotton industry.

Kuyichirchik district is located in the most remote and lowest area of the region, consistent with the meaning of its name. As a result, underground seepage from neighboring and surrounding districts accumulates in this area. Due to these natural conditions, the lands of the district are considered fertile. In some areas, groundwater rises to a depth of 1.5–2 meters. Given the current conditions, rice farming and fishery development in the region could yield favorable results.

However, cotton and grain production in the district has consistently lagged behind. Twelve years ago, the cotton cultivation plan was fulfilled for the first time; prior to that, the district had lagged behind in all agricultural areas. Last year, the district led the region in fulfilling the cotton production plan. In particular, as a result of the efforts of the “TCT Agrocluster” cluster, a total of 30,013 tons of raw cotton were grown in 2019, fulfilling the state contractual plan by 111 percent. The average yield was 32 centners per hectare.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In general, the advantage of the cluster system is that it allows for the sale and export of finished products, which are beneficial to both the state and the manufacturer, rather than raw materials. Another advantage of the cluster system is that enterprises can freely utilize the products they produce and independently determine prices and sales volumes, taking into account the interests of all employees.

Both raw material suppliers and processors are responsible for the quality of the product, as part of the added value generated by the sold product is distributed among all workers who contribute to the overall process. Furthermore, the production process itself generates employment opportunities.

Practice shows that the formation of clusters contributes to the active development of regions and the deepening of interregional integration. A cluster is “attached” to a specific area and relies on its resource potential. A cluster with the same name in one region may differ in form and content from a cluster with the same name in another region. From this perspective, clusters are unique economic structures.

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